

A black and white photograph of a sea ice field. The ice consists of numerous small, rounded floes of varying sizes, some with dark patches of rock or sediment. The water between the floes is dark and shows some ripples. The sky is a uniform, light grey. Overlaid on the upper part of the image is a colorful sunburst graphic with yellow and pink rays. Below the graphic, the text "miracles of nature" is written in a pink, cursive font, and "Pinngortitami tupinnartuliat" is written in a blue, cursive font below it.

miracles of nature
Pinngortitami tupinnartuliat

Aqutsisoq: Ann Eileen Lennert
Assilliisartog: Luca Berti
Allaaserinnittoq: Nikki Schmidt
Tapersiisut: Suleqatigiisitsinermi ingerlatseqatigiit
peqataasuupput EU HORIZON projekt-meersut
GreenFeedBack
Nutserisoq: Ane Johanne Zeeb Skifte

Lead: Ann Eileen Lennert
Photographer: Luca Berti
Scriber: Nikki Schmidt
Contributors: The workshop participants and consortium
of the EU HORIZON project GreenFeedBack
Translator: Ane Johanne Zeeb Skifte

Miracles of nature
Pinngortitami tupinnartuliat

Pinngortitami tupinnartuliat

Pinngortitaaq igalaatta silataaniittoq inunnt pingaarutiliuvoq. Oqaluttuarisaanermi pinngortitaaq sunneeqataanikuuvoq, tamannalu allannguitsivoq. Pinngortitap tunniussarisimavai imeq, silaannaq nerisassallu minguitsut, taavalu nakorsaatinut sanaassat, atortussiassat illuliallu. Oqaluttuarisaanermi inerititassaattita sullinernit pujoralatsitsinissat pisariaqartilluinnarpai pinngortitami inerikkiartortarnerisa katitsernerat, nunanngortarnerat, kulturikkut inuiaqatigiinnullu pilersinneqartarneri ullumikkut takusartakkagut. Pinngortitap illersortarpaatigut qarsumnersuarnut, silarlunnt aammalu pisunut imaannaangitsunut, uagut inissaqartissimagaangatsigu. Tamakkuupput pinngortitami ataqatigiinnermi pingaarluinnartut tupinnartuliat tunissutigineqartut, ilaatigullu eqqumaffiginerusinnaasagut ilaannikkullu taamaattussaannartut isigilersimasagut. Tamatumunngalu pissutaavoq isigisinnaangisagut paasiuminaassinnaasaramik soorlu silaannaq, aammalu isimik takusinnaangisat soorlu drivhusgassi (GHG).

Drivhusgassit inerikkiartorneri millisarniaraanni pinngortitami inerikkiartornerit illersorneqartariaqartuupput pinngitsoorneqarsinnaangitsut, silaannaap kissakkiartorneranut millisaataasinnaasut. Pinngortitap inerikkiartorneranut inunnt iliuuserisanit sunniivallaarnerit immamut minguitsinerit sunnersinnaasarpaat inerikkiartornernut, GHG-mit paarlaassinerit nunarsuullu angerlarsimaffimmik taajukkatta navianartorsiutigisinnaasaanik.

Uumap saqqummersitsinerup siunertaraa takusinnaangisat malugisinnaangisat iluamik piviusumik ingerlanneqarnissaat. Inuit pinngortitallu ataqatigiisinneqarnissaat siunertarineqarpoq, qanoq iliuuseqartarnissanut, inuttut pissusilersuutigut avatangiisitsinnullu sunneeqataassutsikkut iliuuserisartakkat, paasinnittaatsit, nunarsuarmullu isiginnittariaaseq sinnattorisarlu inuuffigisamut

ataqatigiisilersinnaaneri. Silaannaliortariaatsit inuiaqatigiinnit pilersinneqartartup qaammarsaaffiginissaat. Nutaaliornikkut ersersinniarneqarpoq qanoq GHG aamma pinngortitap inerikkiartorneranut nuna, aput, siku, arnat, inuusuttut, ilisimasaqassuseq, ataqatigiinnermut aaqqissuussat, aalisarneq, ineriartornermut, kultoorikkut kingornussat assigisaallu ataqatigiissaarneqarnerat, aammalu siunissatta suna pisariaqartinneraa sunneeqataaffigisinnaasatsinnillu mianersornikkut iliuuseqartarnerit.

Kissaatigaarpullu GHG-mut tunngasunik soqutiginnititsilersinnaalluta, inerikkiartornermullu sunniutigisinnaasaanik pingaartitatsigut, isiginnittariaatsikkut aammalu ilisimatussutsikkullu silarsuarmut paasinnittaattit sunniisinnaanerillu aallaavigalugit. Tamanna allatut qinigassatut nutaaliornikkullu perusupparput. Assit assiliisartup Luca Berti-p assilarivai, Kalaallit Nunaani 2024-mi sumiiffigisami suliaqarfitsinni. Allaaserisallu makku issittumi suleqatigiisitsinermi saqqummiunneqarnikuupput, taakkuuppullu ilisimassutsikkut paasisat pingaartitallu.

Miracles of Nature

Nature outside our window, is essential for human life. Throughout history we have interacted with nature and this very interaction has altered us. Nature has provided us with water, clean air and food, and raw materials for medicines, industry and buildings. Our crops have throughout history relied on insect pollination and the complex biological processes that create soil, and that in turn created the cultures and societies we see today. Nature has protected us from flooding, storms and extreme events when we have given it space to do so. These are the ecosystem services, nature's fundamental miracles, that it provides us and miracles we often take for granted or are unaware of. Because some things can be difficult to grasp, especially when some things are as thin as air and not visible to see, this goes for greenhouse gasses (GHG).

Mitigating GHG emissions, by protecting these ecosystem services is one of the actions necessary for reducing the impacts of climate change. Nevertheless, increased pressure on ecosystems deriving from human activities across terrestrial, marine and freshwater ecosystems will potentially increase emissions threatening the ecosystem services, GHG exchange and the planet we call home.

This booklet is based on an exhibition that wishes to make the intangible tangible. It wishes to connect humans with the environment, our role and entwined relationship to our surroundings and how our actions, perceptions, worldviews, dreams for the future shapes our surrounding world. It wishes to bring forward the delicate interconnection we humans have with GHG. It wishes to creatively visualise how GHG and ecosystem services is entwined with landscapes, snow, ice, women, youth, knowledge, infrastructure, fisheries, development, cultural heritage etc. and how our futures impact and depend on this fragile interaction.

We wish to bring more awareness in relation to GHGs and ecosystem services and how our values, worldviews and knowledge shapes our understanding and impact of our surrounding world. This we wish to do in an alternative and creative way. The photos were taken by photographer Luca Berti and his analog camera during our fieldwork in Greenland 2024 and the scribes represent the knowledge, perceptions and values shared during our workshops throughout the Arctic.

ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

 the FOUNDATION for our WAY of LIFE

the sea & land has given us WATER, CLEAN AIR, FOOD, MATERIALS & MEDICINE.

ABOUT 70%

of the air we breathe come from the ocean. Maybe it's time we recognize the benefits we get from nature?

GIVEN Opportunity & CREATED traditions

but how do we MAINTAIN BALANCE between HUMANS & NATURE?

CO₂ & preserve CLIMATE MITIGATING conditions & ecosystems?

it PROTECTS us from floods, storms & extreme weather events. Providing a safe home.

Pinngortitamut ataqatigiinnermi iliutsit

Pinngortitamut ataqatigiinnermi iliutsit tassaapput nioqqutissat, iliutsit imaluunniit sanaassat, pinngortitap inunnut tunniussai, pinngortitap ataqatigiinnerata pilersitai. Tamakkuuppullu pilersuisussaanermi iliutsit, naleqqussarnermi iliutsit, kultooreqarnikkut iliutsit aammalu iliutsit tapertaasut allat.

OU5821

GR-12-246

AWT

0301

UKI

50

Ecosystem services

Are the goods, services or products that nature provides to humans thanks to ecosystems. These consist of provisioning services, regulating services, cultural services and supporting services.

CULTURE, TRADITION & LIVELIHOOD

What nature provides us with is so closely intertwined with culture. For many communities along the coast, what you harvest from nature is not only food, it also plays a key role in traditions, and creates important bonds between families, individuals and elders. It embodies people's symbolic ties to the environment and knowledge based on these environments throughout history.

-It is an identity, culture and lifestyle.

Kultoori, ileqqut inuuniutillu

Pinngortitap tunniuttagai kultoorimut atassuteqarluinnarput. Sineriak sinerlugu amerlasuut pinngortitami pilersortarput, nerisassaannaanngitsunik aammalu qitiusumik ileqquni pingaartitsinermi ilaqutariinnut, inuit ataasiakkaanut utoqqarnullu attaveqaatinik qanillititsisartut. Pinngortitap inuiaqatigiillu ataqatigiinnerat ilisarnaatitut atanerat poortarpaa aammalu oqaluttuarisaanermi ilisimalikkat aallaavigisarlugit.

-Tassaavoq kinaassuseq, kultoori inooriaaserlu.

Culture, Tradition and livelihoods

What nature provides us with is so closely intertwined with culture. For many communities along the coast, what you harvest from nature is not only food, it also plays a key role in traditions, and creates important bonds between families, individuals and elders. It embodies people's symbolic ties to the environment and knowledge based on these environments throughout history.

-It is an identity, culture and lifestyle.

SNOW & ICE

a **GLACIER** starts with a **SNOWFLAKE**

SNOWFALL
dynamics

can impact microbial
decomposing processes
realising green house gases.

THICKER
snow

more isolation
& more thaw.

the reflection
of sunlight.

Creates
a cooling
effect

more exposed dark surfaces,
more absorbed light,
leading to higher temperatures.

THE OLDEST
ICE CORES
store ancient
bubbles of air
& CO₂ going back
800,000
years

**SHORTER SNOW & ICE
COVER PERIODS**
speeding up rising
surface temperatures.

ICE PROVIDES
humans with
fresh water,
livelihood &
hunting grounds
on frozen sea &
fjords.

SOUND

less ice makes the
water noisier, impacting
species sensitive to
sound, disturbing
ecosystems.

THE ICE
tells a story
about our
**HISTORY &
FUTURE.**

Aput sikulu

Uagutsitulli uumasut nipinik oqaloqatigiittarput. Qanittumi paasineqarut malillugit issittumi imeqarfiit/imaqarfiit tassaasimapput nipit nalinginnaasut, soorlu immami uumasogafinni, aalisakkani, arferit imaluunniit allat immami uumasut nipiliortariaasiinut attaveqariaasiinullu nalinginnaasut, soorlu nerisassarsiormi, piaqqiornermi, attaveqaaqatigiinnermi aammalu sumiissusersionermi. Immalli iluani nipit sikumit pisut (nipinik tigooraasut) allannguuteqarput sermersuup aakkiartornera peqqutigalugu. Aammattaaq umiarsuarnit nipiliornerit, aatsitassalerivinni misissuisarfiit aammalu angallannikkut ineriartorneq ilutigalugu allannguutaasuni peqqutaqaataapput immami nipit assingani. Siunissami pinngortitaq kisimi sunnerneqarnavianngilaq, issittumi inuiaqatigiit aamma sunnerneqassapput, taakku sineriak angerlarsimaffittut taagugaat, piniartarfiat, pilisarfiat aammalu aalisartarfiat pineqarput, taakkuuppullu kultoorikkuinnaanngitsoq inuuniarnikkulli tamaani piunissamut aalajangeeqataanerpaasusaaq.

-Sermeq nittaallamit aallaaveqarpog

Snow and Ice

Like us, animals communicate through sound. Until recently, most Arctic waters were

home to naturally occurring sounds that marine life, fish, whales or other marine animals, could interpret and rely upon for activities like feeding, mating, communicating and navigating. But the underwater soundscape has changed due to the sea ice melting (sea ice absorbs noise and sounds). Additionally, noise from intensifying rates of shipping, oil and gas exploration, and infrastructure development also play their toll on the soundscapes under the surface of the sea. In the future this will not only impact nature but also the people of the Arctic that call these coasts their home, where hunting, harvesting and fishing not only have a cultural connection but also is crucial to be able to live there.

-A glacier starts with a snowflake.

The Landscape

the **TOP 3 METERS** of soil is estimated to store **1000 petagram** of organic carbon. **MORE** than is contained in the atmosphere.

Nunap isikkui

Issittumi sumiiffinni amerlasuuni nunarsuarmi nioqqutissaqarnerata pisariaqartitsinerulerneranik, nukissiuteqarfiit pilersinneqartarnerinut, uumasut nerisaqarneritigut, peqqinnartunik nerinissamut nunalerinikkut atorfissaqartitsinerit aammalu nerisassioriaatsikkut nerukkaatissanillu nutaaliormi annertuumik nunamik atuiffiusumi kissassutsit qaffasinnerusut ullullu aasakkut qaamanertuneri pinngortitami iliuitsinut nalinginnaasunut sunniuteqaqataapput. Atorfissaqartisineq tamanna matussuserniarlugu nunarujussuit atortariaqarneranut soorlu nunalerinikkut, innaallagjissiusornikkut imaluunniit atortulersuusersornikkut ineriartortinneqarsimavoq. Taamaasilluni aamma pinngortitamut ineriartuutinut iliuitsit immikkuullarissuserlu arlalitsigut sunnerneqarput. Tamannalu kinguneqartarpoq pinngortitap kulstof-mut illersornissamut pisinnaassusaanik millisarneqarneranik, silap allanngorpallaannginnissaanut millisaatit, kiisalu kulstof ukiorpassuarni toqqortap iperarneqarneranik. Tamakkulu allannguutit aamma pinngortitap uninngatitsisinnaaneranut, isugutammi milluaasinnaaneranut imermillu nakkartitsisinnaaneranut allanngueqataasarput. Naasoqarnikkut allannguutit aamma sorlaqarnikkut ilutsit nunamiittut allanngortittarpai. Ataatsimut isigalugu tamakku qarsutinersuarnik, panernersuarnik, nunap sisoorneranik aammalu pinngortitap neriuinermik kinguneqarsinnaallutik.

The Landscapes

In many places of the Arctic global market demands, renewable energy implementations, demand from grazing animals, new agricultural needs following an emphasis on 'eating green', and new opportunities for food and fodder production at high latitudes due to rising temperatures together with the long daylight periods in summer, -are putting human pressure on the natural ecosystems. To meet these demands the use of the land is changed by e.g. agricultural use, wind power production, or extending the infrastructure to support these new developments. By this ecosystem services and biodiversity are impacted in many ways. Often, it results in loss of nature's ability to store carbon and mitigate climate change and can also lead to release of carbon that has been stored for thousands of years. These land-use changes additionally alter nature's ability to store, absorb moisture and filter waters. The change in vegetation alters the root systems in the soil. Together these can result in flooding, droughts, landslides and erosion.

The men

2-4 times faster
WARMING SEAS
in the arctic.
Resulting in changing currents & ecosystems, shrinking fishing & hunting grounds, affecting mens lives.

more ENVIRONMENTS & human wellbeing are INTERTWINED

1000
AFFECTED economically & culturally by GLOBAL WARMING

Uses nature for TRADITIONAL fishing & livelihood.

LOW IMPACT & CO₂ emissions

HUMAN ACTIVITIES HAVE A **BAD IMPACT.**
like machines & roads disturbing natural environments affecting GHG emissions balance.

Angutit

Issittumi angutit amerlasuut piniarnikkut aalisarnikkut inuuginnarnissamut pisariaqartitsisuupput.

Pinngortitap ineriartorneranut tamaviaartitsineq, soorlu uumasut sumiiffinniit nikittarnerannut, aalisakkallu ikiliartornerannut aammalu sikup pissusaanut siulittuuteqarsinnaanerup innarliineranut peqqutaaqataavoq, qulaanilu taaneqartut ulorianarnerulersillugillu tatiginaannerulersippai. Assersuutitut taasinnaavarput ilitsoqqussaralugu sikumik, silap allanngortarneranik ilisimasat tatiginaanneruleralluttuinnarput avatangiisit allanngortarneri peqqutigalugit. Ilitsoqqussaralugu sammisat inooriaatsimut annikillitsineri kinaassutsimut siunniusimasanullu allanguuteqartitsipputtaaq.

Minnerunngitsumillu amerlanerit periarfissanik nutaanik ujartuinerit pilersinneqarput, allanngueqataallutilu. Periarfissat taakku piujuaannartitsisumik atorneqaleraluarpata pinngortitamut annikinnermik sunniuteqartussanngussagaluarput, avatangiiserisarput, pinngortitap tupinnartuliai pigiinarsinnaagaluarpai, uagullu aamma ikiorluta.

The men

Many men in Arctic communities rely on hunting, fishing, and herding for subsistence and income. Pressures on the ecosystem services has altered animal migration patterns, reduced fish stocks, and made ice conditions unpredictable, making these activities more dangerous and less reliable. An example of this is that traditional knowledge of ice conditions and weather patterns is becoming less reliable due to rapid changes in the environment. As traditional activities become less viable, men may face challenges in adapting to new roles or finding alternative livelihoods, which can affect their sense of purpose and identity. Nevertheless, many do see new opportunities also arising due to change of environments, new resources that nature provides being available and urbanization. If done in a sustainable way these opportunities can have a low impact on the nature that surrounds us and let nature keep its many miracles that help us along the way.

The Women

CULTURE bearers

managing sustainable practices in fishing & hunting.

their TRADITIONAL LIVELIHOODS helps preserving carbon-storing environments

GLOBALISATION

bringing new habits & activities, contributing to

TRANSPORTATION emissions

Environmental CHANGE

FORCING them to find NEW LIVELIHOODS

WOMEN ARE ACTIVE AGENTS of CHANGE

as educators, administrators and policymakers, women bring DIVERSE PERSPECTIVES and innovative ideas that are key for an equitable and sustainable planet.

per person in GREENLAND 11,36 t CO₂ (2023)

Arnat

Arnat tassaapput allannguinessamut sulisut. Ilitsersuisutut, ataqatigiissaarisutut aammalu aaliangiisussat, isiginnittariaatsit assigiinngitsunik nutaaliornernullu isumassarsianut, taakkuuppullu piujuartitsinissamut naapertuulluinnartumik aaliangeeqataasut. Aammalu arnat pingaarutilittut inissisimapput ilitsoqqussaralugit ilisimasanik piujuaannartitsisussatut, soorlu nerisassiornikkut, atisatigut, aammalu inuiaqatigiit peqqissusaannut. Arnanut unamminarsigaluttuinnaalertussaavoq ilisimasanik ingerlatitseqqiisarnerit kinguaariit inuusunnernut pissutsit allanngorartut peqqutaallutik, allanut nuttarnert, avatangiisit allanngorneri aammalu nunarsuarmi siammarterneq peqqutaalluni. Qanoq inuinnarnissamut allannguutaavoq, nittartakkatigut aammalu ataatsimooriaatsit sunneeqataanerit peqqutigalugu. Qanoq pinngortitamut paasinnittaaseqarnitsinnut aamma sunniuteqarput. Puigussanngilarpullu pinngortitamik ataqqinninneq/pingaartitsineq tassaaginnannginnami avatangiisermik atatitsineq

-tassaasorli nassuerutiginninnermik, inuinnarnissamik inuunerullu akornani peqqissutsimut pilersuisinnaanermullu inunnut nunarsuarmullu ataqatigiinnermik.

The Women

Women are active agents of change. As educators, administrators, and policymakers, women bring diverse perspectives and innovative ideas that are key for an equitable and sustainable planet. At the same time, women often play an important role as care keepers of traditional ecological knowledge, including skills related to food preparation, clothing, and community well-being. It is becoming more challenging for women to pass on knowledge to younger generations due to not only changing environments, but also globalization and urbanization playing a toll. There is a change in how we live, the influence of the internet and social media, and an influence on how we perceive and value nature. We should not forget that valuing nature is not just about preserving the environment,

-it's about recognizing the interconnectedness of all life and ensuring the survival, health, and prosperity of both humans and the planet.

the HARBOUR

the heart of the town

the **LINK** where **PEOPLE** & the **MARINE ECOSYSTEMS** connect.
Due to few greenlandic roads the water is the main choice for transportation.

where **GENERATIONS** meet.

relying on **STABLE CONDITIONS**

MELTING ICE

OPENS NEW Shipping routes, MORE TRAFFIC & EMISSIONS & extended use of THE HARBOUR

EXTREME WEATHER & RISING SEA LEVELS
→ a need for infrastructure upgrades

OIL SPILLS

& vessel emissions through combustion as well as increased traffic affects the ecosystems.

Umiarsualivik illoqarfiup uummataa

Umiarsualivik issittup sineriaani amerlasuuni illoqarfiup pisoqarfigisarpa. Tamaani kinguaariit naapittarput piffik nipeqalaartuaannartoq aalisakkanik neqinillu qaqsivik uummaarilluartartoq. Umiarsualivik aamma assersuutissaqqippoq pinngortitap qanoq tunniussaqaarsinnaassusaanut soorlu nerisassanik atortussanillu. Inuuffissaqqissunik qanoq tuniorartarneraatigut aalisakkanik, pinngortitallu inerikkiartorsinnaassusaanik atatitsilluarnissamut takussutissanik. Umiarsualivimmi ersarippoq pinngortitap tunniussarisartagai ilitsoqqussanut assigiinngitsunut, ileqqunut, inuulluataarnermut kiisalu ilisimasaqassutsikkut avitseqatigiinnermi naapisimaarnermi eqqartortakkat soorlu sila, kuit, ullorlu imarsiornemi nalaalluagaq, aalisarneq imaluunniit motori aallarumangikkaangitsoq.

The Harbour -the heart of town

The harbour is the heart of many communities along the coasts of the Arctic. It is where generations meet, fish and meat are landed and it's a place of life, a constant summing. The harbour is also a clear example of how nature provides us with resources, such as food and materials. How nature supports us by obtaining habitats for the fish we fish and helping us keep healthy ecosystems. In the harbour it is evident how nature provides to many cultures and traditions, wellbeing, but also knowledge exchange, as we meet and talk about the weather, currents, a good day at sea, fishing or the motor which did not start.

Fishing

Depend on a healthy marine ecosystem.

Trawling

traditional

WARMER OCEANS & RETREATING GLACIERS makes fish move **NORTH** -

A tug of war between north & south.

Changing the fish population.

DESTROYS SEA BOTTOM

releasing large amounts of CO₂ stored in the sediment.

using old methods helps to protect carbon absorbing marine life. Low CO₂ impact.

Aalisarneq

Pinngortitap tunniuttagai amerlapput, aalisarnerlu tassaavoq pilersuinermut qitiusoq. Aammalu naleqqussaataavoq immap naqqa tassaammat kulstof-nik annerpaanik toqqortaqarfik. Kilisaatillu immap naqqani kilisakkaangata kulstof imaanut akuleruttarluni taamaalilluni ukiumut 0,3 gigaton immap naqqanit akulerunneqartarpoq. Kulstof taanna immap naqqaniittut akulerunnerata kingunerisarpai uumassuseqarnermut annertusaanernut pinngortitap uumassuseqarneranut akerliusumik sunniuteqarneq. Aammattaq umiartornikkut atortut amerliartortillugit uumassuseqarnerit innarlerneqartarput. Aaliangeeqataasussatullu inissisimavoq uumasooqassuseq qitiusumik siunertaqarmat, kulstof-nik katersinerinnaannginnami aammalu toqqorteriviinnaannginnami, kisiannili allannguutit sunniutaannut illersuutaavoq silaannaap allanngoriartornerata kinguneranik ingalassimaartitseqataallunilu silap pissusiata allangorujussuarnissaanut illersuutaallutik. Pinngortitaannaanngilarli sunnerneqartartoq, uagullumi aamma sunnerneqartarpugut, aalisagakilliornermi sinerissami inuussutissarsiorneq aamma kalluarneqartarmat aammalu iliuitsinut oqimaaqutaalluni, pinngortitap silaannarmut avatangiisinullu nalimmassartarneranut.

Fishing

Nature provides us in many ways and fisheries contribute as the main provisional service of the sea. Whereas, it contributes as a regulating service with the sea bottom as one of the largest deposits of stored carbon. But when fishing boats trawl the ocean floor, the stored carbon is re-released pumping out up to 0.3 gigatons of carbon every year. The carbon released from the seabed into the water can increase ocean acidification and affect productivity and biodiversity negatively. Additionally, over harvesting of marine resources puts a strain on the biodiversity of the fished areas. This is crucial, as biodiversity plays an important role not only in carbon uptake and the storage of carbon, but also as a buffer and natural guard for mitigating the changes happening in connection with climate change, such as natural barriers for extreme weather events and storm floods. In the end we do not only impact nature but also ourselves, as lack of fish will impact livelihoods along the coasts, together with the strain of services nature provides to adjust to climate and environmental change.

INFRASTRUCTURE & URBANISATION

99% of Nuuk's energy comes from **HYDROPOWER**
In 2030 the goal is that 80-85% of Greenland's usage, aiming for 100% in the future.

more **IMPORTS** & a **GROWING** population leads to an increase of **CO₂**

TRYING to **AIM FOR** green energy

a need for **MORE ROADS** INFRASTRUCTURE & HOUSING

Less land that cycles green house gases.

infrastructure is **KEY**

to build a **SMART SYSTEM** that can support **HUMAN EVOLVEMENT** & preserve necessary natural systems.

Atortulersuutit aamma illoqarfinngorsaanerit

Silaannarmut naleqqussariaatsit pinngortitap nammineq iliuuserisartagai aammalu sunniuteqarfigisagai pinngotitमित पिसुपुत. Soorlu aalisakkat immap naasuinik nerigaangata kulstof aalisakkamut sunniuteqartarpoq, immap naasuata katersorsimasaanik. Silaannaap allanngoriartorneranulli illersuutaasinnaallutik immap naasuisa pujoralaasa kulstof-nik katersisarnerat, taamaasillutik aamma illersuutaalluarlutik silap allanngorartup neriuineranut.

Immap naqqa allanngoraangat atortulersuineq ilaliussinerlu sineriammi qaffattarpoq. Tamanna siunissami sunneeqataasussaavoq imaanut inuussutissanut mingutsitsinermut. Illuatungiliuttumik sunniuteqartarnera sakkukillisittarpaat, uumassuseqarnermut sunniuttarmat aammattaaq kulstof-ip ingerlaarneranut. Kisiannili amerlasuutigut pinngortitap ikiortarpaatigut, iluaqutissartaalu uagut pisariaqartippagut.

Infrastructure and Urbanization

Climate regulating services are nature-based solutions that is nature's way to mitigate and buffer the impacts of climate change. This can be by fish eating kelp and taking up the carbon that the kelp has stored into their bones and scales. It can be microorganisms and algae cleaning the water, and by kelp and seaweed protecting shores from erosion during extreme weather events caused by climate change. As seascapes change, urbanization and infrastructure along the coasts will increase. These will in the future contribute to an increase in nutrients and pollution entering the sea. It will weaken nature's ability to buffer the changes, impacting biodiversity, the carbon cycle, but also impact many of the ways in which nature helps us and its many benefits we depend on.

Getting replaced
by SNOWMOBILES

The SLED DOG

they need
COLD CONDITIONS

Shorter winters
means **LESS
DOG USE.**

the dogs are connected to
**IDENTITY, ENVIRONMENTAL
KNOWLEDGE & CULTURE**

due to **CLIMATE CHANGE** both
the sled dog & the culture
that goes with it are threatened
by **EXTINCTION.**

It is a sustainable
mean of transport

THRAWLING
makes it harder to
FIND FOOD for
the dogs.

less **ICE** → less **DOGS**
& fertilization

Qimuttut

Kalaallit qimmii qimuttut immikkuullarissuupput. Tassaavoq qimmeq kultoorikkut periutsikkullu ukiut 4.000-nit amerlanerusut kristusip inuunerata siulianinngaanneersut. Periuseq piujuaannartitsisooqataavoq pinngortitamullu avatangiiserisatsinnut sunniuteqartarnera minnerpaaffimmiilluni. Ileqquuvoq ilisimatussutsikkut atorreqarnermigullu immikkuullarissusilik, ilisimaneqarporlu angallannikkut, suleqatigiinnikkut aammalu pilersuinikkut qimussimik nunakkut imaatigullu atorreqarnerani. Ukiorpassuarni avatangiisip pissusaanik allannguutinillu ataqatigiisitsineruvoq, ilaatigullu piffissaq sivikinnerusumi qimussersinnaaneq nammineq nerlersuutissanik pilersornikkut unamminartoqartitsisarmat, akil qaffakkiartortut, nerlersuutissat suliarineri pisariuleraluttuinnarneri aammalu iliuutsit unammilligassat amerliartornerisigut. Soorlu snescooteriinnaanngitsut aammali ileqqut allanngoriartorneri kinaassutsimik ilisimasanillu aarlerinaateqalersitsipput. Tamakkuuppullu assersuutitut atorreqarsinnaasut, uumassuseqarnermut sunniutinut, pinngortitap tunniussinnaasaanut aammalu inuuffigisatsinnut kultoorikkut, ilitsoqqussanut, angalasarnernut, nunap ilusaanut ingerlavigisartakkanut sunnerneqartarnerannut.

The Sledgedog

The Greenland sledge dog is a unique breed. It is a dog breed, culture and technology that dates back more than 4,000 years before Christ. It is a technology which both is sustainable and has a minimal impact on the vast nature surrounding. It is a culture that spans from the knowledge and use of this tough breed, but also knowledge connected to travels, interaction and harvesting when traveling with dog sleds through land- and seascapes. Due to a combination of changing environments, change of seasons and shorter periods one can dog sled, difficulties in being self-sufficient in dog food, rising prices of processed food, and the competition from new technologies such as snowmobiles, threatens not only the dog breed, but also the culture, identity and knowledge connected to the breed. This is a clear example of how a change of ecosystem services impacts the way in which nature provides us with resources and habitat, but also how it safeguards culture, traditions and the means of how we travel and know the landscapes we travel through.

The youth

THEIR VOICES & actions will SHAPE the FUTURE.

Growing up in a **RAPIDLY CHANGING WORLD** due to CLIMATE CHANGE

DREAMING of what they want: closeness to nature, more activities, healthy oceans

IDEAS SOLUTIONS

Playing a crucial role in in **GREENLAND'S RESPONSE & ADAPTATION** to environmental changes.

* the SNOW they play in now might not stay on the ground for long when they get older.

The young are more inclined to **EXPLORE** possibilities of **NEW TECHNOLOGIES**

creating **AWARENESS** and spreading **KNOWLEDGE** across generations of the connection between nature & traditional **WAYS of LIVING.**

Inuusuttut

Allanguinermut aallartitsisuusarput inuusuttut. Taakku siunissamut matuersaat paaraat. Issittumi sumiiffinni arlalinni inuusuttut aquttutut, naligiisitaanermut, suleqatigiinnissamut suliniutinut sassartarput. Inuusuttut nutaaliornikkut nalimmassartarput silallu allanngoriartorneranut soorlu iliuitsit allat atorlugit avatangiisinik nakkutilliinerit ataqatigiissaartarpaat, ilitsoqqussaralugu ilisimasat nutaanngorlugit. Tamakku siuttuunissaannut pisariaqartippagut tatiginninnermik ineriartortitsinermut naligiissaarinernullu.

The youth

Youth are catalyst of change. They hold the key to the future. Many places in the Arctic, youth are stepping up as leaders and advocate for both equity, equality and taking climate action as a collaborative effort. Young people are finding innovative ways to adapt to climate change, such as using technology to monitor environmental changes or combining traditional knowledge with modern science. For this we need to build trust and transparency and help them lead the way.

Workshops

We have held creative workshops with youth, elders, students, researchers, local and indigenous people, and administrators - people from many different geographical areas and with different backgrounds.

Our motto is: The more diverse, the merrier. Here, we have shared and discussed knowledge, perceptions, connection to and the value of the sea, nature, opportunities, challenges, how these impact the ecosystems services we depend on, how and what we should prioritize, and how we achieve our goals in a good and ethical way.

We worked with different sheets, drew and discussed in groups. We mapped values, how we see the place we live in the future, its legacy, and how can we work together to fulfill our future dreams in balance with nature. We created spaces for listening and being heard and hopefully we have helped create awareness and common understanding for the many different perceptions, values and worldviews that shape the coast in the Nordics and the Arctic. Because we need this understanding and recognition when we talk about ecosystem services, climate change and how the future will be shaped.

-It requires equity, equality, compromises and mutual understanding.

Suleqatigiippiit

Nutaanik pilersitsisinnaanermut suleqatigiisitsinikuuvugut inuusuttut, utoqqaat, ilinniartut, ilisimatusartut, sumiiffimmi innuttaasut aammalu nunat inoqqaavi peqatigalugit – inuit nunanit allaneersut tunuliaqutillillu assigiinngitsut peqatigalugit. Oqartarpugut uagut – amerlanerugutta pitsaanerussaaq. Uani immikkoortissimavagut eqqartorlugillu paasisat, paasinnittaatsit, ataqatigiinnerit immamullut naleqartitat, pinngortitaq, periarfissat, unammilligassat qanoq pinngortitamut ataqatigiisumik sunnerneqartarneri pisariaqartinnerlugit aammalu qanoq pingaarnersiuisanerluta anguniakkatta pitsaasumik ileqqorissaartumillu angusaqarsinnaanerluta. Skemat assigiinngitsut atorlugit suliaqarsimavugut, titartaanerit oqallinnerillu immikkoortitaarluta.

Pingaartitanik allattuinkuuvugut, qanoq inooriaatsimut isiginnittariaaseqarnerluta, siunissami kingornussisussaataitaanermullu qanoq suleqataasinnaanerluta pinngortitaq peqatigalugu.

Inissaqartitsisimavugut tusaaneqarnissamut tusarnaarneqarnissamut neriullutalu ikiuisimassalluta soqutiginnitsitsilersimassallutalu paasinnittaatsinut ataatsimoorussanik, pingaartitat isiginnittariaatsinillu assigiinngitsunik, ilusilersueqataasussanik nunani avannarlerni issittunilu. Paasinnittariaaseq akuersaarnertu taamaattoq pisariaqartipparput, uumassusilerinermi iliuutsinik, silaannaap allanngoriartorneranut qanorlu siunissap ilusilersornissaanut eqqartuinissamut.

Assigiissuseq, naapertuilluarneq, naaperiaasissaaneq aammalu illugiittumik paaseqatigiissinnaanermik piimasaqateqarpoq.

The Workshops

We have held creative workshops with youth, elders, students, researchers, local and indigenous people, and administrators - people from many different geographical areas and with different backgrounds.

Our motto is: The more diverse, the merrier. Here, we have shared and discussed knowledge, perceptions, connection to and the value of the sea, nature, opportunities, challenges, how these impact the ecosystems services we depend on, how and what we should prioritize, and how we achieve our goals in a good and ethical way.

We worked with different sheets, drew and discussed in groups. We mapped values, how we see the place we live in the future, its legacy, and how can we work together to fulfill our future dreams in balance with nature. We created spaces for listening and being heard and hopefully we have helped create awareness and common understanding for the many different perceptions, values and worldviews that shape the coast in the Nordics and the Arctic. Because we need this understanding and recognition when we talk about ecosystem services, climate change and how the future will be shaped.

-It requires equity, equality, compromises and mutual understanding.

